

Synthesis and mechanism of anti-scaling effect of itaconic acid/allyl sulphonic acid/acrylic acid terpolymer[†]

Yueqin Yu^{a,b*}, Zhongzhen Li^b, Aixiang Dong^b, Shusheng Zhang^b and Pingkai Ouyang^a

^aCollege of Life Science and Pharmacy, Nanjing University of Technology, Nanjing 210009, People's Republic of China

^bCollege of Chemistry and Molecular Engineering, Qingdao University of Science and Technology, Qingdao 266042, People's Republic of China

E-mail : yyueqin@126.com

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Abstract : The optimum ratio of monomers, itaconic acid (IA) : allyl sulphonic acid (ASA) : acrylic acid (AA) and conditions of their polymerization to produce the terpolymer for scale removal in experimental water was determined using the orthogonal experiment. The optimum conditions of the terpolymer syntheses were as follows : the monomer ratio IA : ASA : AA = 2 : 1 : 4 (wt.), the initiator (APS) 4.5% (wt. of total monomers), the chain transfer agent (*i*-propanol) 9.5% (wt. of total monomers), the reaction time 1.5 h, the reaction temperature 95 °C. The IR spectra of the terpolymer confirmed that there was no olefinic band at 1635–1620 cm⁻¹. The IA/ASA/AA terpolymer presented excellent scale inhibition to CaCO₃. As the concentration of Ca²⁺ is 1600 mg L⁻¹ in experimental water and the addition of the terpolymer is 10 mg L⁻¹, the inhibition of the terpolymer is 95.88%. The mechanism of anti-scaling effect of IA/ASA/AA terpolymer has been put forward.

Keywords : Itaconic acid, anti-scaling effect, synthesis, mechanism.

The utilization of water with inorganic impurities, and processing of crude oil-water mixture containing such impurities, is plagued by precipitation of these impurities with subsequent scale formation.

Most industrial waters contain calcium, barium, magnesium, etc. cations and bicarbonate, carbonate, sulfate, oxalate, phosphate, silicate, fluoride, etc. anions. These salts precipitate on surfaces of the water carrying system, and form scales or deposits. This accumulation prevents effective heat transfer, interferes with fluid flow and facilitates corrosive processes and harbors bacteria. This scale removal problem is expensive in many industrial water systems causing delays and shutdowns for cleaning and removal.

Numerous compounds have been added to the industrial waters in an attempt to prevent or reduce scale and corrosion¹. One such class of materials is the well known organophosphates, which are illustrated by the compounds hydroxyethylidene diphosphonic acid (HEDP) and

phosphonobutane tricarboxylic acid (PBTC). However, the organophosphates would cause the phosphate scale, and even cause the industrial water nutritious for microbial growth which suffocates higher aquatic life forms. Fortunately, copolymers or terpolymers containing acrylic acid (AA) segments can play an important role in inhibiting scale formation in industrial water system, which is more environmentally friendly than currently available scale inhibitors. The purpose of this work was to investigate synthesis of the itaconic acid (IA)/allyl sulphonic acid (ASA)/acrylic acid (AA) terpolymer, and study the mechanism of their anti-scaling effect.

Results and discussion

Orthogonal experiment : The experiment was designed using a multiple-factor statistical design method : orthogonal experimental design². This method offers more reliable outcome and fewer experimental trials compared with the conventional single-factor experimental design. We selected the experimental factors as follows : the initiator

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(APS) dosage (% weight of total monomers); the chain-transfer agent (isopropanol) dosage (% weight of total monomers); the monomer ratio IA : ASA : AA (wt.) and the reaction time. A total of four factors, each with three different levels (Table 1) were selected in the study, using the orthogonal-design method. An experimental design with nine trials was chosen for this study (Table 1). The scale inhibition efficiency of the terpolymer obtained in each trial and maximum difference analysis are listed in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively.

Data R (maximum difference of I_i) in Table 2 showed that the influence of monomer ratio IA : ASA : AA (wt.) on the scale inhibition of the terpolymer was the most remarkable, the influence of the initiator on the scale inhibition of the terpolymer was the secondly remarkable, the influence of the chain-transfer agent on the scale inhibition of the terpolymer was the third remarkable, the influence of reaction time was the most unapparent. It was showed from Table 1 that the largest scale inhibition of the terpolymer was 95.88%, which corresponded to the best conditions of the synthesis of IA/ASA/AA terpolymer as follows : the monomer ratio IA : ASA : AA = 2 : 1 : 4 (wt.), the initiator 4.5% (wt. of total monomers), the chain-transfer agent 9.5% (wt. of total mono-

mers), the reaction time 2.0 h. Because the influence of reaction time on the scale inhibition of the terpolymer was not apparent, we can select the reaction time as 1.5 h. Then, the alone recipe and time are optimum. It showed that IA/ASA/AA terpolymer had good scale inhibition to CaCO_3 . When the concentration of Ca^{2+} is 1600 mg L^{-1} in experimental water and the addition of terpolymer is 10 mg L^{-1} , the inhibition of the terpolymer is 95.88%.

In IR spectra of IA/ASA/AA terpolymer, there was a strong band at 3433 cm^{-1} due to O-H stretching vibration and a band at 1728 cm^{-1} due to C=O stretching vibration, 1403 cm^{-1} due to C-O stretching vibration of COOH groups. The $-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$ in ASA units were revealed by a band S=O at 1179 cm^{-1} , S-O at 798 cm^{-1} , and C-S at 636 cm^{-1} , 532 cm^{-1} . There was no olefinic band at 1635 ~ 1620 cm^{-1} .

Scale inhibition efficiency of IA/ASA/AA terpolymer in different initiator dosage was measured as shown in Fig. 1, when we maintained the other synthesis conditions as follows : the monomer ratio IA : ASA : AA = 2 : 1 : 4 (wt.), the chain transfer agent 9.5% (wt. of total monomers), the reaction time 1.5 h, the reaction temperature 95 °C. With the increase of initiator dosage, the

Table 1. Experimental design $L_9(3^4)$

Experiment	Initiator (% wt.)	Chain-transfer agent (% wt.)	Monomer ratio IA : ASA : AA (wt.)	Reaction time (h)	Scale inhibition (%)
1	4.5	5.5	4 : 1 : 2	1.5	67.82
2	4.5	9.5	2 : 1 : 4	2.0	95.88
3	4.5	7.5	3 : 1 : 3	2.5	59.42
4	6.5	5.5	2 : 1 : 4	2.5	64.83
5	6.5	9.5	3 : 1 : 3	1.5	63.00
6	6.5	7.5	4 : 1 : 2	2.0	55.81
7	8.5	5.5	3 : 1 : 3	2.0	59.69
8	8.5	9.5	4 : 1 : 2	2.5	59.47
9	8.5	7.5	2 : 1 : 4	1.5	74.93

Table 2. Maximum difference of I_i

Factor	Scale inhibition (%)			R
	I_1	I_2	I_3	
Initiator (% wt.)	74.37	61.21	64.70	13.16
Chain-transfer agent (% wt.)	64.11	72.78	63.31	9.47
Monomer ratio IA : ASA : AA (wt.)	61.03	78.55	60.70	17.85
Reaction time (h)	68.58	70.46	61.24	9.22

Notes : I_i - Scale inhibition rate for i level of certain factor, respectively.

R (the maximum difference of I_i) = $I_{\text{most}} - I_{\text{least}}$.

scale inhibition efficiency of terpolymer also augments. But when the initiator dosage rises to a certain value, its scale inhibition efficiency reaches to a maximum value. If the initiator dosage continues to augment, the scale inhibition efficiency begins to decrease. When the initiator dosage in IA/ASA/AA terpolymer synthesis test is 4.5%, the scale inhibition efficiency is about 95.88%.

Fig. 1. The effect of initiator dosage on scale inhibition efficiency

The average zeta-potential of the sediment particles obtained from scale inhibition test above was shown in Fig. 2. We can see that the effect of initiator dosage on

Fig. 2. The effect of initiator dosage on the average zeta-potential of sediment particles

average zeta-potential of sediment particles corresponds with its effect on the scale inhibition efficiency. We can come to the conclusion that the IA/ASA/AA terpolymer can improve the average zeta-potential of sediment particles which makes small sediment particles separated from one another. The shape and size of the sediment particles obtained from scale inhibition test treated with terpolymer and untreated with terpolymer are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 respectively.

Fig. 3. TEM images of sediment particles obtained from scale inhibition test treated with terpolymer

Fig. 4. TEM images of sediment particles obtained from scale inhibition test untreated with terpolymer

Then, the mechanism of anti-scaling effect of IA/ASA/AA terpolymer can be described as follows. Firstly, the IA/ASA/AA terpolymer is adsorbed on the growth sites of the sediment crystal altering its growth pattern so that the crystal are formed more slowly and highly distorted. Secondly, the terpolymer adsorbed on the surface of the sediment particle can improve the average zeta-potential of sediment particles, it reinforces the repulsion between the particles thus it disperses solids and prevents precipitated crystals from agglomerating and depositing on the surfaces of storage vessels.

Conclusions :

Using orthogonal experimental design, the optimum conditions of synthesis of IA/ASA/AA terpolymer were determined as follows : the monomer ratio IA : ASA : AA = 2 : 1 : 4 (wt.), the initiator 4.5% (wt. of total monomers), the chain transfer agent 9.5% (wt. of total monomers), the reaction time 1.5 h, the reaction temperature 95 °C.

The IR spectra of the terpolymer confirmed that there was not olefinic band at 1635–1620 cm^{-1} .

The IA/ASA/AA terpolymer had good scale inhibition to CaCO_3 . When the concentration of Ca^{2+} is 1600 mg L^{-1} in experimental water and the addition of terpolymer is 10 mg L^{-1} , the inhibition of the terpolymer is 95.88%.

Experimental

Materials : Ammonium persulfate (APS), isopropanol and the vinyl monomers such as IA, ASA and AA were all 99.5% pure and provided by Beijing Chemical Company (China) and used without further purification.

Preparation of the terpolymer : The polymerization of IA/ASA/AA terpolymer was carried out in a 100 mL glass reactor fitted with a stirrer, condenser, thermometer, and droplet funnel. IA (6.0 g, 0.046 mol), ASA (3.0 g, 0.024 mol), isopropanol (2.0 g, 0.03 mol) and deionized water (20 mL) were added in the reactor. The mixture was stirred, and heated to 95 °C by means of an external heating jacket. Then the AA (12.0 g, 0.162 mol) and APS (0.95 g, 4.2 mmol, in 10 mL deionized water) were drop-fed into the reactor respectively over a period of 2.0 h, maintaining a temperature of 95 ± 2 °C. At the end of the AA and APS addition, a temperature of 95 °C was maintained for an additional 1.5 h and then cooled to room temperature.

Scale inhibition effect : Stock solution A : 33.00 g/L NaCl, 12.15 g/L CaCl₂·2H₂O, 3.68 g/L MgCl₂·6H₂O.

Stock solution B : 33.00 g/L NaCl, 7.36 g/L NaHCO₃, 0.03 g/L Na₂SO₄.

Stock solutions A and B were saturated with CO₂ over a period of 30 min. 0.5 Milliliter of 0.1% (wt.) scale inhibitor solution was added into each 50 mL stock solutions of A and B, then these mixtures were kept at 70 °C for 30 min in a water bath. The solution A was mixed with solution B in the flask, and the mixture was kept at

70 °C for 25 h in a water bath, cooled to room temperature. The content of the flask was filtered. The soluble calcium in filtrate was titrated with EDTA to a bright violet end point using murexide as indicator. Sufficient indicator should be added to turn the solution to a bright rosy pink color. Inhibition is calculated from the following equation :

$$\text{Inhibition \%} = \frac{V_1 - V_0}{V - V_0} \times 100\%$$

where V_1 is milliliter EDTA for scale inhibitor-treated mixture and kept in water bath; V is milliliter EDTA for blank, untreated, not kept in water bath; V_0 is milliliter EDTA for blank, untreated, and kept in water bath.

The sediment obtained from above filtering operation was dispersed in deionized water. The average zeta-potential (ξ) of sediment particles was determined by using of a zeta-sizer 3000 at room temperature (23 ± 1 °C). The shape and size of the sediment particles were observed through the transmission electron microscope (TEM, TEM-100CX II).

References

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